

Gas-liquid Chromatography of Some Natural Coumarins

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Gas-liquid chromatographic behaviour of twenty two natural coumarins have been studied on different polar and non-polar columns. Optimum conditions regarding column length, concentration of the stationary phase, carrier gas flow-rate and column temperature for the separation of these compounds on each type of column have been established. Correlation between the structures of some of the compounds and their retention values have been observed.

Though there are number of publications on paper chromatography¹⁻⁷, paper electrophoresis⁸ and thin-layer chromatography⁹⁻¹⁴ (TLC) of coumarins, very little work has been done on the gas-liquid chromatography (GLC) of this important class of compounds. Recently Brown and Shyluk¹⁵ as well as Furuya and Kojima¹⁶ have studied a number of coumarins by GLC. The present communication deals with the separation of twenty two natural coumarins by GLC on different types of polar and non-polar columns.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus : A "Dual column F & M Gas Chromatograph Model 700" equipped with a dual flame-ionization detector and a Honeywell Electronik-15 potentiometer recorder (full scale 1 millivolt) was used.

Column preparation : To prepare the column packing material, the solid support "gas chrom P" (60-80 mesh) was coated with the stationary phases separately in the following way. The required amount of stationary phases taken in 500 ml round bottom flasks was dissolved in a volume of a suitable solvent sufficient to cover the solid. Toluene in case of silicone rubber (SE-30) and apiezon L (APL) and chloroform for diethylene glycol adipate polyester (DEGA) were used as the solvents. The required amount of solid support was slowly introduced into the flask and the whole system was stirred thoroughly to obtain uniform slurry. The solvent was then evaporated in a rotating vacuum evaporator under suction of a filter pump until the slurry was dried to a free flowing powder. The last traces of solvents were removed by heating at 80° for 2 hr in a vacuum oven. The following columns were prepared by packing different lengths of aluminium tubing of 4 mm bore with the packing materials thus prepared.

- (1) 2 and 6 feet long 10% silicone rubber (SE-30)
- (2) 2 and 6 feet long 10% diethylene glycol adipate polyester (DEGA)
- (3) 2 and 6 feet long 10% Apiezon L (APL)
- (4) 2 feet long 5% Apiezon L (APL).

Each of these columns was conditioned for 16 hr at its maximum permissible temperature while the carrier gas flow rate was kept at 45 ml/min.

Samples : Twenty two coumarins taken for this study, the names and structures of which are given in Table I were divided into two groups. Group I contained coumarins of simple molecular structures and without any phenolic hydroxyl group. This group

TABLE - I

STRUCTURAL FORMULAE OF COUMARINS			
COMPOUNDS	STRUCTURE	COMPOUNDS	STRUCTURE
<u>SIMPLE COUMARINS</u>		<u>FURANO COUMARINS</u>	
1. COUMARIN		12. ANGELICIN	
2. HERNIARIN		13. PIMPINELLIN	
3. AESCULETIN DIMETHYL ETHER		CHROMENO α -PYRONES	
4. MARMIN		14. XANTHYLETIN	
5. SCOPOLIN		15. LUVANGETIN	
6. AYAPIN		16. SESELIN	
<u>FURANO COUMARINS</u>		<u>4-PHENYL COUMARINS</u>	
7. PSORALEN		17. DALBERGIN	
8. XANTHOTOXIN		18. NOR-DALBERGIN	
9. BERGAPTEN		19. MESUOL	
10. MARMESIN		20. ISO-MESUOL	
11. BYAKANGELICIN		21. DIMETHYL MESUOL	
		<u>3-PHENYL COUMARIN</u>	
		22. TRI-O-METHYL WEDELO LACTONE	

Me = METHYL $R_1 = -CH_2-CH=C(CH_3)CH_2-CH(OH)-C(CH_3)_2OH$

Ph = PHENYL $R_2 = -CH(OCH_3)_2OH$ $R_3 = -O-CH_2-CH(OH)-C(CH_3)_2OH$

$R_4 = -CH_2-CH=C(CH_3)_2$ $R_5 = -CO-CH(CH_3)_2$

included coumarin, herniarin, angelicin, psoralen, ayapin, aesculetin dimethyl ether, seselin, xanthotoxin, bergapten, xanthyletin, pimpinellin and luvangetin. The group 2 contained coumarins of higher molecular weight and of more complicated molecular structure and included scopolin, marmin, dalbergin, nor-dalbergin, byakangelicin, marmesin, mesuol, isomesuol, dimethyl mesuol and tri-*o*-methyl wedelolactone. Luvangetin of the group 1 was also included in this group as an internal standard.

TABLE II

Relative Retention Times of Coumarins (Group 1) on Various Columns (Herniarin = 1)

Compounds Structures	SE-30	SE-30	APL	APL	APL	DEGA	DEGA	GS
	10% 6ft 200°	10% 2 ft 200°	10% 6ft 250°	10% 2ft 200°	5% 2ft 200°	10% 6ft 200°	10% 2ft 200°	12% 2ft 108° (Brown & Shyluk)
Coumarin	0.45	0.36	0.40	0.38	0.49	0.20	1.00	0.29
Herniarin	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Angelicin	1.12	1.00	1.40	1.00	1.00	1.16	1.21	1.00
Psoralen	1.35	1.29	*	1.17	1.11	1.43	2.10	1.65
Ayapin	1.57	1.57	*	1.17	1.11	2.84	2.43	
Aesculetin di- methyl ether	2.03	1.92	*	1.63	1.52	1.54	2.43	3.15
Seselin	2.19	1.92	*	1.76	1.52	1.26	1.21	1.25
Xanthotoxin	2.52	1.92	*	2.37	1.89	3.00	3.85	3.60
Bergapten	2.66	2.57	*	1.89	3.30	3.85	3.85	3.40
Xanthyletin	2.82	2.57	*	2.62	2.08	2.17	2.43	
Pimpinellin	3.37	3.38	*	3.40	2.40	2.35	2.43	3.10
Luvangetin	4.30	4.63	*	3.92	2.78	3.90	4.93	
Isobergapten								2.50
Sphondin								3.90
Isopimpinellin								6.70

*Did not emerge out of the column.

Gas-liquid chromatography : Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas at 20 p.s.i. Hydrogen and compressed air supplied to the detector were maintained at 20 p.s.i. and 40 p.s.i. respectively. The injection port and the detector were maintained approximately at 30 degrees above column temperature. When steady temperature and flow-rate conditions were reached, the sample in the form of solution (1 to 2 μ l) was injected into the injection port by means of a micro syringe (Hamilton Co. Inc., Whitter, Calif., U.S.A.) and the chromatogram recorded. The retention times were measured from the initial emergence of the solvent peak to the peak of the compound in question.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Of the seven chromatographic columns used, the 6 ft 10% SE-30 and 6 ft 10% DEGA columns were found to be suitable for the complete separation of the coumarins listed in group 1 at the optimum column temperature of 200°. The polar DEGA column required

a much higher flow-rate than the non-polar column for comparative resolution. The respective chromatograms are represented in fig. 1A & B. Shortening of the lengths of both DEGA and SE-30 columns decreased the degree of resolution. From the relative retention times (t_R) of the compounds of group 1 represented in Table II one can find that the sequence in which the compounds came out of the non-polar SE-30 column was changed when the polar DEGA column was used. Thus whereas, seselin came out between xanthotoxin and aesculetin dimethyl ether from the 6 feet non-polar SE-30 column, it appeared between angelicin and psoralen when the 6 feet polar DEGA column was used. Similarly xanthyletin and pimpinellin had t_R between those of bergapten and luvaugetin on non-polar column

but from polar column these two came out between ayapin and aesculetin dimethyl ether. The sequence of the t_R in the non-polar column is according to the volatility of the compounds as the non-polar column separate compounds according to their boiling points. With the polar columns the t_R mainly depends upon the polarity of the compounds. So it is expected that the t_R of coumarin derivatives on these columns will change according to the nature and number of groups attached to the coumarin nucleus. One fact is very clear from the Table 2 that the t_R on polar column increased with the number of methoxyl substituents in the molecule of the compound concerned. These observations agree with the findings of Narasimhachari and Von Rudloff¹⁷ as also with those of Brown and Shyluk¹⁵. Of the 18 natural coumarins studied by Brown & Shyluk, some had also been included in the present work. The last column of Table 2 contains the relative retention times quoted from their paper. The structures of isobergapten, sphondin and isopimpinellin used by these authors are given as above. Furuya and Kogima¹⁶ could also separate a number of hydroxy coumarins after converting them into trimethyl silyl ethers.

If the retention data given in Table II are considered it can be observed that in the case of furano-coumarins, the position of furan ring in the structure influenced the retention values on the polar columns to a large extent. The structure in which the furan ring is attached to the 7 and 8 position had much lower t_R than the isomeric compound with the furan ring attached to 6 and 7 position; in other words the angular coumarins had lower t_R than the linear ones. Thus angelicin had a lower t_R than psoralen, t_R of isobergapten was much lower than that of bergapten and xanthotoxin. Pimpinellin emerged long before isopimpinellin. In the case of chromeno- α -pyrones also, the t_R of seselin with pyrone ring at 7 and 8 position (angular type) was much lower than that of xanthyletin with the pyrone ring at 6 and 7 position (linear type). In the case of isomeric mono-methoxy coumarins the different positions of methoxyl group in coumarin structure had influence on t_R . The

TABLE III

Relative Retention Times of Coumarins (Group 2) on Various Columns (Luvangetin = 1)

Compounds	SE-30	SE-30	APL	APL	APL	DEGA	DEGA
	10% 2ft	10% 2ft	10% 6ft	10% 2ft	5% 2ft	10% 6ft	10% 2ft
	300°	280°	250°	250°	250°	200°	200°
Scopolin	0.78	0.66	*	0.60	0.64	*	
Luvangetin	1.00	1.00	*	1.00	1.00	*	1.00
Marmesin	1.17	1.22	*	2.01	1.17	*	1.00
Byakangelicin	1.43	1.73	*	2.90	2.84	*	1.14
Marmin	2.60	2.00	*	3.96	3.87	*	1.14
Dalbergin	3.17	2.37	*	4.98	4.84	*	1.41
Nor-Dalbergin	5.07	2.81	*	7.21	7.03	*	1.77
Dimethylmesuol	6.07	4.50	*	9.02	8.58	*	2.36
Isomesuol	*	6.72	*	12.35	12.13	*	3.18
Mesuol	*	8.00	*	14.50	14.06	*	3.77
Tri-o-methyl-wedelo- lactone	*	10.12	*	19.60	18.90	*	4.45

* Did not come out of the column.

Fig. 1

- A. Gas chromatographic separation of a mixture of twelve coumarins of group 1 on a 6 ft. 10% SE—30 column. Temp = 200°. Carrier gas (N₂) flow rate = 42 ml/min. S = solvent, 1 = coumarin, 2 = herniarin, 3 = angelicin, 4 = psoralen, 5 = ayapin, 6 = aesculetin dimethyl ether, 7 = seselin, 8 = xanthotoxin, 9 = bergapten, 10 = xanthyletin, 11 = pimpinellin, 12 = luvangetin.
- B. Gas chromatographic separation of a mixture of twelve coumarins of group 1 on DEGA column (6 ft. 10%). Temp. = 200°, carrier gas flow rate 45 ml/min, S = Solvent; 1 = coumarin, 2 = herniarin, 3 = angelicin, 4 = seselin, 5 = psoralen, 6 = ayapin, 7 = xanthyletin, 8 = aesculetin dimethyl ether, 9 = xanthotoxin, 10 = xanthyletin, 11 = bergapten, 12 = luvangetin.
- C. Gas chromatographic separation of a mixture of eleven coumarins of group 2 on 2 ft. 10% SE—30 column. Temp. = 280°C, N₂ flow rate = 40 ml/min, 8 = solvent, 1 = Scopolin, 2 = Luvangetin, 3 = marmesin, 4 = byakangelicin, 5 = marmin, 6 = dalbergin, 7 = nor-dalbergin, 8 = dimethylmesuol, 9 = isomesuol, 10 = mesuol, 11 = tri-o-methyl wedelolactone.

compounds with methoxyl group in 5 or in 8 position had lower t_R than the compound methoxylated in 6 or 7 position. Amongst the monomethoxy coumarins sphondin with methoxyl group in the 6 position had the highest t_R even higher than that of pimpinellin which contained two vicinal methoxyl groups.

For the separation of the coumarins included in group 2 none of the longer columns were found suitable. Decrease in the length of the columns improved the separation of these compounds to a large extent. Thus they could be separated very well using the 2 ft 10% SE-30 column at 280° and carrier gas flow rate around 45 ml/min (fig. 1C.). Increase or decrease of either column temperature or carrier gas flow rate caused overlapping or trailing of the peaks respectively. Complete separation of the same compounds was also obtained with the 2 ft 5% APL column but with considerable broadening of some peaks even at 250°, the highest permissible temperature for this column; this broadening of peaks increased when the 10% APL column was used. Their retention values in Table III showed that the order of emergence of these coumarins from the columns did not change with a change in the polarity of the stationary phases, but these values increased with the corresponding increase in the number of hydroxyl groups, particularly the phenolic hydroxyl in their structures. In the present investigation the phenolic coumarins like dalbergin, nor-dalbergin, mesuol and isomesuol could be satisfactorily separated on both non-polar SE-30 and polar DEGA column, each 2 ft long, at 280° and 200° respectively. Alcoholic hydroxyl group in the structure also increased the t_R of coumarins, though to a much lesser extent than the phenolic hydroxyl. Byakangelicin and marmin both having two alcoholic hydroxyl groups in the side chains had higher t_R than that of marmesin containing only one such group.

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REFERENCES

1. T. Swain, *Biochem. J.*, 1953, **53**, 200.
2. D. P. Chakraborty and P. K. Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 905.
3. W. L. Fowlks, *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, 1959, **32**, 249.
4. B. Acacic, D. Kustrak and B. Poje, *Planta Med.*, 1961, **9**, 70.
5. T. Beyrich, *J. Chromatog.*, 1964, **13**, 181.
6. W. Steek and S. H. Wender, *J. Chromatog.*, 1965, **19**, 564.
7. S. Berlingozzi and V. Parrine, *Sperimentale, Se. Chem. biol.*, 1956, **6**, 59.
8. J. Dutta, H. C. Chakraborty and B. K. Barman, *Sci. and Cult.*, 1962, **28**, 84.
9. W. L. Stanley and S. H. Vannier, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 3488.
10. E. Stahl and P. J. Schorn, Hoppe-Seylers, *Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1961, **325**, 263.
11. R. A. Bernhard, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1171.
12. C. F. V. Sumere, G. Wolf, H. Teucky and J. Krit, *J. Chromatog* , 1965, **20**, 48.
13. F. M. Abdel-Hay, E. A. Abu-Mustafa, B. A. H. El-Tawil and M. B. E. Fayed, *Planta Med.*, 1965, **13**(1), 91.
14. J. Dutta, M. Hoque and D. P. Chakraborty, *J. Chromatog.*, 1969, **42**, 555.
15. S. A. Brown and J. P. Shyluk, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **34**, 1058.
16. T. Furuya and H. Kojima, *J. Chromatog.*, 1967, **29**, 382.
17. N. Narasimhaehari and E. M. Rudloff, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1962, **40**, 1123.